

FLIGHT DYNAMICS EVALUATION FOR THE T3 SUBORBITAL FLIGHT TEST

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ABSTRACT

Almost 10 years after the first successful landing of a Falcon 9 booster, reusability of first stages is still a feature that only SpaceX has been capable to master. Nevertheless, reusability is now part of the baseline design of several launch system currently under development, in the US and China. In this context, the SALTO project, funded by the European Commission and coordinated by ArianeGroup (AGS), aims to raise the maturity level of the first European reusable rocket technology.

On one side SALTO will perform, for the first time in Europe, hop-flight tests of a small-scale reusable rocket first-stage demonstrator – named the T1H – to validate the landing phase. In parallel, key technologies will be developed to be integrated in the next suborbital flight vehicle – named the T3. In particular, the T3 will be a large-scale demonstrator that will fly at very high-altitude in the atmosphere and perform all the most relevant maneuvers that are needed to return and recover the first stage of a launcher. During the test mission, it will fully control its attitude making use of grid fins and thrust vector control.

Deimos' contribution to SALTO includes support to the aerodynamic design of the T3 taking the responsibility of the flight qualities analysis and of the control laws assessment for the suborbital test mission. The trimmability, stability and controllability of the vehicle is evaluated during the full flight envelope to support several iterations of the aerodynamic design. In addition, the feasibility of the suborbital mission is studied in detail and the trajectory optimized to increase the representativity of the suborbital flight test with respect to dynamic conditions that a reusable booster will have to face during the return path. Finally, Deimos will also continue the development of state-of-the-art control laws initially developed in the RETALT project and adapted to the T3 scenario, that are being tailored to the suborbital mission and will be tested up to TRL 5.

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Index Terms—launchers reusability, flight mechanics, re-entry trajectory, SALTO

1. INTRODUCTION

Currently, launch vehicle reusability is the most effective method for reducing the cost of space access, a crucial factor in the commercialization of space [1]. However, it remains a significant technical challenge, with only two U.S. companies—SpaceX and Blue Origin—successfully developing the technology for routine launcher recovery missions. Both employ retro-propulsive vertical landing as their recovery strategy and report substantial cost savings from reusability. In this context, the reusable strategic space Launcher Technologies & Operations (SALTO) project, funded by the European Union (grant agreement No. 101082007) aims to raise the maturity level of the first European reusable rocket technology. Within SALTO, Deimos' contribution includes the flight dynamic analysis and the design and development of control laws for reusable launchers.

The objective of the flight dynamic analysis in SALTO is to support the aerodynamic design of the T3 configuration and evaluate the feasibility of the suborbital test mission.

To meet the study objectives, and based on Deimos' experience in atmospheric flight and re-entry mission analysis [2][3][4], at first the flight dynamic evaluation focuses on the analysis of the capability of the T3 configurations to perform such a mission. In this preliminary *mission feasibility analysis*, the characteristics of the suborbital mission are evaluated with respect to key design parameters to support the identification of design points and ensure the representativeness of the flight test against the expected flight envelope for the operational launcher.

Once the flight envelope for the return mission has been identified, the *mission design* of the reference mission can be performed in detail. The flying qualities analysis and flight dynamic analysis allow to evaluate the controllability, trimmability, and stability characteristics of the T3 configuration during the different mission phases, and derive requirements for the consolidation of the reference mission design. The reference trajectories for the suborbital scenario are thus optimised to support the development of the different technologies necessary to enable the recovery and therefore the reusability of the launcher, in particular the control laws.

2. REFERENCE CONFIGURATION

The baseline configuration and main focus of this paper is T3, a ~30 m tall large-scale model of the 1st stage of a heavy Vertical Takeoff Vertical Landing (VTVL) launcher, shown in Figure 1. The goal of the suborbital flight tests is to reproduce all the phases that are needed by an operational reusable launcher that uses retro-propulsion for the recovery of the 1st stage. The vehicle operates similarly to a typical launcher during ascent until Main Engine Cutoff (MECO). After that, the test scenario resembles a Downrange Landing (DRL) recovery scenario, illustrated in Figure 2, with a final landing at sea on a floating barge. After a flip over maneuver is executed close to peak altitude, the vehicle enters the first active aerodynamic descent phase enabled by the use of Aerodynamic Control Surfaces (ACS). Then, a re-entry burn is executed, to reduce velocity and limit the peak dynamic pressure, followed by a second active aerodynamic descent. Finally, pinpoint soft vertical landing is enabled by an engine-powered descent.

Figure 1: T3 descent configuration (credits: AGS/DLR).

Figure 2 T3 suborbital flight test concept

The concept configuration of the T3 vehicle integrates 3 Prometheus engines and has a dry mass of about 24 tons and about 55 tons of propellant available.

CFD analyses were carried out by DLR in the context of SALTO to deliver dedicated aerodynamic databases for all T3 configurations [5].

3. MISSION FEASIBILITY ANALYSIS

The mission feasibility analysis of the T3 focuses on the assessment of the capabilities of the proposed configuration to perform the suborbital flight test mission. The exploration of the flight envelope identifies the conditions that the vehicle will face during the flight test.

The analysis of the flight capability is carried out studying the different maneuvers to identify design drivers for the suborbital mission and to contribute to the consolidation of the propellant budget. The mission needs are identified in terms of performance required to ensure the representativeness of the flight test with respect to the expected conditions that the 1st stage of an operational reusable launcher will have to face during re-entry. Figure 3 shows the reconstructed velocity-altitude profiles of several Falcon 9 (F9) missions [6]; in addition, the reference trajectory for the reusable RETALT1 configuration as proposed in [4] is also reported, as well as the original reference trajectory for T3 preliminarily defined by Ariane Group. The return mission of F9 is characterized by a re-entry burn that is triggered between 2.4 and 1.3 km/s, approximately. RETALT1 has a re-entry burn that starts at 2.3 km/s. On the contrary, the re-entry burn of the reference T3 trajectory occurs at a much lower altitude and velocity. This strategy will allow testing the capability of the vehicle to perform the burn, and the related operations.

Starting from this initial reference, an exercise was performed to understand the impact in terms of design parameters (in particular, the additional propellant required) to increase the velocity and altitude at which the re-entry burn occurs, with the ultimate goal of reproducing during the T3 test the operational conditions expected for the recovery of the first stage of this class of launchers. For instance, the ascent burn (R1) and the re-entry burn (R2) could be redefined to bring the aerodynamic phase as close as possible to an operational scenario, while the landing maneuver (R3) is needed to perform a soft landing. For example, Figure 4 shows the result of an assessment where the R1 burn R1 duration was increased by 10s with respect to the original reference to increase the overall energy of the trajectory. Varying the duration and throttling level of the engine during the R2 burn would allow performing the subsequent aerodynamic phase with a velocity-altitude profile that could fall within regions that show similarities with the expected operational conditions of the considered launchers. The propellant consumption required by the R1+R2 burns could be the same or even decrease with respect to the reference one. In addition, the propellant needed to achieve soft landing after R3 is also computed as function of duration and throttling. In this case, performance are similar to the original reference.

With this methodology, it is possible to create several performance maps to assess immediately the impact of the different design parameters on the representativity of the mission and on the mission needs. In this way, different requirements or constraints (e.g. minimum burn duration) could be factored in to ultimately identify design points of interest for the consolidation of the T3 flight test concept.

Two examples are shown in Figure 4, one guaranteeing a minimum R2, R3 burns duration of 10s, which would allow targeting return conditions close to F9's (yellow dot), and the other that maximizes the representativity with respect to the expected return dynamic conditions of RETALT1.

Figure 3 Reconstructed velocity-altitude profiles of several F9 missions, and reference conditions for RETALT and for the T3 flight experiment.

Figure 4 Performance maps obtained assessing the impact on the flight envelope of the different propulsive maneuvers: velocity-altitude performance (left), propellant consumption as function of burn duration and throttling level for R2 (center) and R3 (right)

4. MISSION DESIGN

4.1. Grid fin control strategy

Grid fin control is critical throughout the re-entry, especially during the aerodynamic phase. It is a key mechanism for stabilizing the vehicle's roll, pitch and yaw moments during descent. The implemented control law maps each local grid fin deflection to equivalent aileron, elevator and rudder functions, enabling coordinated control over all three rotating axes.

The standard grid fin configuration resembles an *X-wing* layout, where the fins rotational axes are phased at a 45° angle relative to the fuselage longitudinal and lateral planes. Within this configuration, each single local grid fin rotation affects all three rotational moments simultaneously.

Alternatively, a different configuration has been defined and studied. This configuration follows a *+-wing* layout, where the grid fins rotational axes are aligned with the vehicle's longitudinal and lateral planes (see Figure 5). This orientation decouples the pitch and yaw control channels, assigning dedicated symmetrical rotations to independently achieve pitch and yaw moments. However, the configuration inherently provides reduced control authority in both channels compared to the *X-wing* layout, as only half of the grid fins contribute to each axis. Nevertheless, authority is not expected to be linear and may suffer from shadowing in case of non-zero AoA. A comparative analysis between both configurations has therefore been conducted to quantify their relative performance (see Table 1).

While the standard *X-wing* configuration yields higher moment values, the *+-wing* exhibits only a 29.85% and 26.81% reduction in pitch and yaw authority respectively, despite acting only with two out of the four grid fins. This leaves additional control margin available for perturbation rejection or another actuation demands.

Figure 5 Graphic representation of the *X-wing* and *+-wing* configurations

Table 1 Aerodynamic moment performance from the *X-wing* and *+-wing* configurations. $AoA_T=180^\circ$, Roll = 0° , Mach = 2

	Channel	CLL_{CoG}	CM_{CoG}	CLN_{CoG}
<i>X wing</i>	Roll	0.30348	0.05022	-0.01064
	Pitch	-0.00079	2.41782	-0.01064
	Yaw	-0.00079	0.05022	2.29691
<i>+ wing</i>	Roll	0.30348	0.04303	0.02798
	Pitch	-0.00263	1.69595	0.04921
	Yaw	0.00104	0.06426	1.68090

4.2. Post-MECO flight dynamics analysis

After MECO, the T3 vehicle flies ballistic phase up to apogee, where a flip maneuver is performed and the ACS are deployed to face the re-entry phase. Non-negligible aerodynamic effects, due to the relatively low altitude at MECO (40 km in the initial reference provided by AGS), combined with the launcher's statically unstable configuration during ascent, create a particularly challenging situation for the RCS, as the only available means of control. The instability arises from the center of pressure being located ahead of the center of gravity, a consequence of the vehicle's mass distribution at this stage of flight.

A controllability assessment has been carried out to analyze the attitude evolution of the T3 during this phase, to support the RCS sizing and the consolidation of the control strategy. A 6-DoF open loop propagation was conducted starting from MECO. Figure 6 shows the body angular rates of the T3 for a propagation of 110s, in nominal conditions. Results show the pitch body rate grow above 10 deg/s after only 10s.

Figure 6 Nominal body angular rates (p, q, r). Ballistic ascent phase

A Monte Carlo analysis has also been carried out to account for different uncertainty fields (aerodynamic and MCI), showing a much worse situation, and providing a sensitivity insight around the nominal case. The most destabilizing uncertainty groups were examined, with results highlighting the aerodynamic uncertainties (on both force and moment coefficients) as well as uncertainties in the CoG and inertia matrix. In contrast, mass uncertainties were found to have no significant impact on the vehicle's attitude evolution.

4.3. Entry Corridor analysis

The trimmability and stability of the system - Flying Qualities Analysis (FQA) - are evaluated to support the definition of a trim strategy, with the objective of proposing a trim solution based on the mission needs. This is done through the identification of the AoA Entry Corridor (EC), defined as the region of the Mach-AoA plane compatible with a set of flight mechanics constraints considered, that identifies the area within which a trim solution can be identified.

A Monte Carlo analysis is then carried out to assess the performance of the flight and the robustness of the trim solution in non-nominal conditions. Different groups of uncertainties have been taken into account, namely aerodynamics, guidance, MCI and TVC. The presence of uncertainties reduces the viable area within the flight corridors. When these uncertainties become too significant and close the corridors, two mitigation strategies have been analysed: reducing aerodynamic uncertainties and exploring backwards positions of the CoG to increase control lever arm.

The analysis focuses on the re-entry phases of the T3 mission, namely: re-entry burn, aerodynamic phase and landing burn. The FQA tool available in DEIMOS is used [7] for this analysis. For the T3 the FQA covers both the longitudinal and lateral planes, providing a detailed 6DoF analysis. Trim control is provided by grid fin authority and, when available, thrust vector control (TVC).

4.3.1. Aerodynamic re-entry phase

Figure 7 shows the entry corridor during the aerodynamic phase, both for nominal and perturbed (Monte Carlo) conditions. Nominal results provide a trimmable area for AoA between 170° and 180° for the full Mach number range considered. The EC is constrained by the saturation of the grid fins. Nevertheless, no viable solution exists from Mach numbers 3 to 3.5 for any AoA when uncertainties are applied. Grid fin control proves insufficient under these circumstances.

Figure 8 shows the two-mitigation process considered to open the entry corridor between Mach 3 to 3.5 also when uncertainties are considered. On the left, halving the aerodynamic uncertainties considered makes grid fin control sufficient to find a viable trim solution, opening the corridor for AoA between 174° to 180°. Alternative, on the right, it is shown how the increase on the control lever arm generated by shifting rearwards the CoG also opens the corridor in the critical Mach number region, though only for a narrow AoA range.

Figure 7 Nominal (left) and Monte Carlo (right) AoA entry corridors. Aerodynamic phase.

Figure 8 Monte Carlo entry corridors, aerodynamic phase. Halved aerodynamic uncertainties (left) and CoG displacement (right).

As mentioned, the results obtained are based on an aerodynamic assessment of the T3 vehicle performed by DLR. The AEDB considered for the analyses reported in this paper is a preliminary version based on low-fidelity simulations. A consolidation of the characterization of T3 aerodynamic characteristic is currently ongoing, based on high-fidelity CFD simulations and considering also the feedback provided by FQA.

4.3.2. Re-entry burn phase

To reduce the T3 vertical velocity two engines are activated during this phase. The engines enhance the control authority of the T3 by introducing additional control modes through TVC and throttling, supporting the grid fin control. Figure 9 shows the nominal entry corridor for two different TVC angles, -5° (left) and $+5^\circ$ (right). The viable area of the corridor in terms of AoA shifts according to the TVC direction, ranging from 160° - 175° for -5° TVC to 180° - 190° for $+5^\circ$ TVC. The corridor remains bounded by the grid fin saturation limits. Throttling, as a means of control authority, do not have a meaningful impact over the trimmability of this phase.

4.3.3. Landing burn phase

The last part of the re-entry uses one active engine to slow down the vertical velocity until moments before touchdown. For this phase only one engine enhances the control authority with the use of TVC and throttling, as additional control modes, supporting the grid fin control. Figure 10 shows the nominal entry corridor for two different TVC angles, -5° (left) and $+5^\circ$ (right). Like the re-entry phase, the viable area of the corridor in terms of AoA shifts according to the TVC direction, ranging from 163° - 176° for -5° TVC to 183° - 195° for $+5^\circ$ TVC. The corridor remains bounded by the grid fin saturation limits, although it exhibits wider AoA bands compared to the re-entry burn phase. Throttling, as a means of control authority, does not have a meaningful impact over the trimmability of this phase.

4.4. Mission consolidation

The mission design consolidation for the T3 scenario has been carried out considering the flight capabilities identified. In particular, the capability of the vehicle to control the attitude after MECO is strongly affected by the intrinsic aerodynamic instabilities and the very low altitude at which MECO happens. Relying only on the RCS is considered not an option as the system would be over-dimensioned due to the control needs and the limited thrusters' performance at low altitude. Therefore, alternative strategies were investigated.

One option could be to perform an early flip over right after MECO, deploy the ACS, and use them to control the vehicle. In the re-entry configuration (i.e. engine-first), the launch vehicle is stable at Mach 2.5-3. In addition, the aerodynamics is still non-negligible, and the grind fins could help controlling the vehicle. Nevertheless, the efficiency of the fins would be reducing with the altitude. Moreover, the flip manoeuvre shall be very quick and would require a big RCS (inefficient at low altitude) to do it. This option is thus discarded.

Figure 9 Nominal entry corridors. TVC of -5° (left) and $+5^\circ$ (right) supported by grid fin control. Re-entry burn phase.

Figure 10 Nominal entry corridors. TVC of -5° (left) and $+5^\circ$ (right) supported by grid fin control. Landing burn phase.

On the other side, the highest controllability is guaranteed by the Thrust Vector Control (TVC) when engines are ignited. Therefore, the goal shall be to increase the duration of the ascent burn, and in parallel to increase the altitude at which MECO is performed. To do so, and to avoid increasing too much the energy of the trajectory (and therefore the propellant consumption), a partial MECO is required, where one or two engines are turned off. In particular, if the goal is to maximise the altitude at MECO without increasing the propellant consumption, the throttling shall be at the minimum, and only one engine shall be active. Figure 11 shows the Mach-Altitude profile for two trajectories computed with the updated Prometheus engine model:

1. Assuming that no partial MECO is performed, and trying to reproduce ArianeGroup's original reference.
2. Assuming that partial MECO is performed, turning off two of the three engines when the altitude reaches 20 km.

The updated engine model has a better thrust performance with respect to the engine used to produce the original reference. To try to obtain trajectory conditions similar to ArianeGroup's, it would result in MECO occurring at an even lower altitude. On the contrary, if a partial MECO is commanded, the MECO altitude can be increased by more than 15km. The propellant consumption in the two cases is exactly the same.

Figure 11 Comparison between different ascent burn strategies: without partial MECO (strategy #1) and with partial MECO (strategy #2).

4.5. Reference trajectory update

New reference trajectories have been optimized considering the consolidated mission strategy and the updated vehicle models (AEDB, engine, environment) defined in the context of SALTO. Trajectory optimization is performed with an optimisation tool available in DEIMOS' proprietary Planetary Entry Toolbox (PETbox) [2]. The objective is to define the end-2-end reference mission maximizing the altitude at MECO, ensuring a mass consumption that respects the available propellant, and performing aerodynamic phase, and re-entry and landing burns that maximize the representativity of the flight test. The optimisation variables are the timing and the throttling level of the different burns (ascent, re-entry, and landing), the attitude during the ascent phase and the attitude during the aerodynamic phase.

Consolidated trajectories were produced for both strategies, see Figure 12. Strategy #1 was kept in order not to change assumptions with respect to ArianeGroup's original reference. This strategy would allow to have a similar total ignition time between the three engines. Strategy #3 also consider a partial MECO (like strategy #2 mentioned in previous section), but include as well an AoA manoeuvre during ascent to try to further increase the altitude at which MECO occurs. The consolidated trajectories respect all the mission constraints, with margins to compensate for uncertainties and dispersions. For the second case, a pitch manoeuvre is performed during the ascent phase, and partial MECO (cut-off of the lateral engines) occurs at about 80s after lift-off. In this way, it is possible to increase the altitude at MECO to by about 20km, which will considerably reduce the controllability issues discussed in section 4.1. The mass consumed is in both cases higher than for the original reference. Nevertheless, the mass budget is respected in both cases with some margins with respect to the dry mass. The final load factor value remains above the soft-landing constraint (1.2-1.3 g). This value is limited by the minimum throttling capability of the Prometheus engine. Each burn in the re-entry phase (R2 and R3) meets the minimum ignition time requirement (10 s), and the engines are ignited while maintaining the same operating conditions. Finally, the maximum dynamic pressure condition never exceeds the constraint of 100 kPa. The trim AoA solution for the aerodynamic phase is within the corridor avoiding instability regions.

The consolidation of the reference trajectory with updated models and strategy confirms the feasibility of the mission solution, showing similar performance in terms of trajectory characteristics.

Figure 12 Consolidated trajectories for the T3 flight experiment.

5. CONCLUSIONS AND WAY FORWARD

The mission engineering activities demonstrated that the suborbital flight test of the T3 vehicle is feasible and could also guarantee an adequate representativity of the expected operational conditions.

An analysis methodology was introduced to define and evaluate performance maps for the flight test, and support the identification on promising design points.

The baseline mission identified was consolidated and verified in full alignment with the most detailed vehicles models made available during the activity.

The assessment of the capabilities of the proposed configuration is supporting the consolidation of the aerodynamic characterisation of the T3 vehicle, currently ongoing in the framework of SALTO.

Moreover, the flight dynamics evaluation is supporting also the consolidation of control laws that will be evaluated considering also uncertainties and dispersions. Testing will be performed with Model-in-the-Loop (MIL), Software-in-the-Loop (SIL), and Processor-in-the-Loop (PIL) approaches with the goal of reaching TRL ≤ 5 at the end of the activity.

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